

A low-code crowdsourcing platform to support innovation and increase efficiency

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Abstract

In their attempt to innovate, companies need to develop custom software products that in most cases need to be co-created with end-users. The use of a low-code platform can facilitate this process by allowing requirements gathering based on real interactive mockups designed by non-tech users through the use of a low-code tool. Through this co-creation phase, end-users can navigate on the real mockups and provide valuable feedback. After this co-creation/crowdsourcing phase with stakeholders, the owners of the platform (non-tech users) can easily transform the mockups to software code ready to be deployed. Living labs can consider the use of low-code tools to enhance their portfolio of services.

Key words

#low-code, #mockups, #MVP, #livinglabservices, #innovation, #requirements

Problem statement

In their attempt to innovate, companies need to develop custom software products that in most cases need to be co-created with end-users. However, developing software products is costly and time consuming mainly due to the very limited software engineering resources available worldwide (500K developers are missing from the job market in Europe). At the same time, gathering appropriate requirements is not an easy task and sometimes the methodologies used are not sufficient.

Methods/approach used

We propose the use of WABLI (<https://wabli.eu>), a low-code (and no-code) platform that facilitates rapid prototyping for bootstrapping the design process and generating ready-to-deploy innovative web applications. In WABLI, the approach that is being used is the following:

1. SMEs can easily design the pages of their innovative products. In accordance with best practices in UI prototyping solutions, WABLI allows non-tech users to define the application layout (both web and mobile) in the form of interactive mockups.
2. Stakeholders (citizens, end-users) can now be involved (early in the design process) and can navigate through the real interactive mockups. Stakeholders can provide structured feedback (crowdsourcing) on every single page of the application. They are provided with a clear view of the end product, and they are given the ability to modify and comment all entities in a consistent manner.
3. After the mockups have been refined and approved by the end-users, the owner of the application (non-tech) can easily create the data model of the application. The requirements are automatically being extracted and the application is ready to be deployed.
4. Through WABLI's automatic code generator, back-end (node.js, mongoose, MongoDB) and front-end (HTML, CSS, Javascript) code is automatically being generated. Users can download the source code of their application and deploy it either automatically on WABLI servers or at their premises.

Results/outcomes

Using WABLI, or a similar low-code platform, startups and SMEs can co-create innovative products in a cost-efficient and time-effective manner. End-user

involvement is the key in the development of useful, usable and innovative products and has positive effects on the success of product and user satisfaction. Living Labs can provide to their customers low-code solutions to allow them easily co-create their MVPs.

Why WABLI?

The increasing need of innovation and digitalization is expected to enhance the use of low-code development platforms. The time for low-code is now. WABLI provides the place where startups and SMEs can co-create fully functional data driven web applications on without the support of software developers. WABLI turns non-tech SME employees into software builders. WABLI has been used successfully by startups to create their prototypes. It is important for the public and also for the Living Labs to be aware that such tools exist and can speed up the development of MVPs involving end-users in the design of their products.

It would be interesting to examine whether Living Labs could be interested in such a tool. WABLI could be provided for free at least for one year to all ENoLL members. Living Labs can use WABLI as a service to their customers to allow them co-create their innovative web applications with their end users.

